

Project acronym: RESISTIRÉ

Project title: "RESponding to outbreaks through co-creaTive sustainable inclusive equality stRatEgies"

Grant agreement number: 101015990

Start date of project: 1 April 2021, Duration: 30 months

RESISTIRÉ

Reducing gendered inequalities
caused by COVID-19 policies

Deliverable 6.4

Overall report on Solutions

Due date of deliverable	30/09/2023
Submission date	29/09/2023
File Name	D6.4 RESISTIRE_Overall report on Solutions
Organisation Responsible of Deliverable	YW
Author name(s)	Aart Kerremans (YW), Alain Denis (YW), Grace Romeo (YW), Agnieszka Kolasińska (ISAS), Claudia Aglietti (K&I), and Sofia Strid (ORU/UGOT)
Revision number	01
Status	Final ¹
Dissemination Level	PU ²

Acknowledgement and Disclaimer

¹ Document will be a draft until it is approved by the coordinator

² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101015990.

The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of its author and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

Revision history

Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	29/08/2023	Aart Kerremans, Sofia Strid	Structure & introduction; lessons learned for research agenda
0.2	04/09/2023	Aart Kerremans, Claudia Aglietti, Agnieszka Kolasińska	Expansion of initial draft + integration of lessons learned for factsheets & pilot projects
0.3	05/09/2023	Alain Denis	Comments and expansion
0.4	06/09/2023	Aart Kerremans	Integration of comments
0.5	14/09/2023	Aart Kerremans	Integration of quality review comments
0.6	27/09/2023	Alain Denis	Integration of final comments
1.0	29/09/2023	ESF	Coordinator's check and submission

Partners

ESF
ORU
YW
OBU
K&I
TUD
SU

UDEUSTO
ISAS
Sciensano
UGOT

List of acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CSO(s)	Civil Society Organisation(s)
D	Deliverable
EU-27	European Union (27 countries)
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
NGO(s)	Non-Governmental Organisation(s)
NRRP(s)	National Recovery and Resilience Plan(s)
Q&A	Question and Answer
RA(s)	Research Agenda(s)
RAS	Rapid Assessment Survey(s)
RFO(s)	Research Funding Organisation(s)
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Summary

The aim of RESISTIRÉ is to understand the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak and its policy responses on behavioural, social, and economic inequalities in 30 countries - the EU-27 (with the exception of Malta) plus Iceland, Serbia, Turkey and the UK - and to work towards individual and societal resilience. It does so by mapping policies and social initiatives on the one hand, and collecting quantitative and qualitative data on the other, and by analysing and translating these into insights to be used for designing, devising, and piloting solutions for improved policies and social innovations to be deployed by policymakers, stakeholders, and actors in the field in different policy domains. The project relies on an eleven-partner multidisciplinary and multisectoral European consortium, and a well-established network of researchers in 30 countries.

This deliverable gives an overview of the different processes across all three cycles of the project that led to the development of RESISTIRÉ's various outputs: the operational recommendations, the pilot projects, and the agendas for future research. The operational recommendations, designed as RESISTIRÉ factsheets, focused on 22 topics in total. For the pilot projects, seven different sets of terms of reference were developed over the first two cycles, eventually resulting in nine implemented pilot projects (two for Green Spaces as Ecosystems of Care and two for Engaging with Gender-based Violence Through Sports) across eight different countries. Finally, by the end of the third cycle, sixteen research agendas had been developed as well.

Following the solutions created as part of the project, this report concludes with a section that indicates the various lessons that were learned throughout RESISTIRÉ's three cycles. These lessons are differentiated by task, as the processes for developing the operational recommendations, pilot projects, and future research agendas all markedly differ from each other. They provide an insight into the strong points as well as the difficulties of the solution development processes.

Table of Contents

Deliverable 6.4	1
Summary	4
Table of Contents	5
Introduction	6
Process	8
Operational Recommendations	8
Pilot Projects	10
Agendas for Future Research	12
Results – Operational Recommendations	14
Results – Pilot Projects	16
Results – Agendas for Future Research	19
Lessons Learned	20
Operational Recommendations	20
Pilot Projects	21
Agendas for Future Research	22
Conclusions	25
References	27

Introduction

The aim of RESISTIRÉ is to understand the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak and its policy responses on behavioural, social and economic inequalities in 30 countries - the EU-27 (with the exception of Malta) plus Iceland, Serbia, Turkey and the UK - and to work towards individual and societal resilience. At its peaks, the pandemic led to the introduction of national policy responses and measures in multiple policy domains to slow infections and prevent deaths (Cibin et al., 2021, 2022, 2023). But these responses had unequal effects on individuals and groups, not least those already vulnerable or marginalised (Axelsson et al. 2021; Sandström et al. 2022, 2023). The policy and societal responses profoundly changed lives, with physical and social distancing temporarily becoming the new norm and, where needed, quarantining and self-isolation. This process radically shifted how society is organised, with increased working from home, home-schooling and intensification of online presence, all with their own specific (un)intended consequences (Bonaccorsi et al., 2020). It also meant furloughing and job losses, with associated economic hardship and mental health issues, delayed ordinary health treatments, and worse, the loss of life (Nicola et al., 2020; Van Bavel et al., 2020; Lewnard & Lo, 2020). Worryingly, it also meant increases in the levels of gender-based violence (GBV) and variations in access to support and healthcare.

The impacts of these developments, like those of other crises, are gendered and related to sex, age, disability, ethnicity/race, migration status, religion, social class, and the intersections between these inequalities (Lokot & Avakyan, 2020; Walter & McGregor, 2020; Walby, 2015; Axelsson et al., 2021; Sandström et al., 2022, 2023). They are uneven and unequal, disproportional in their consequences for different groups, and their long-term impacts are still uncertain (Cumming et al., 2020). Women have been disproportionately infected by COVID-19 (Sciensano, 2020) and affected by its impact; as front-line workers, as formal or informal caregivers in society; as exposed to a higher risk of men's violence, in particular as intimate partner violence. As these positions intersect with social class, ethnicity, age and other inequalities, our approach deploys a 'gender+' approach, which highlights gender relations and gender inequalities, but always considers how these intersect with other complex inequalities (Verloo, 2013; Walby et al., 2012). Policy responses to this (and any future) pandemic also need to consider the gender+ perspective, and how some groups benefit, while others lose out. It is important to understand how different policy responses have unequal effects, but also how different measures can be put into place to understand and address gender and intersectional inequalities in different policy domains (Lombardo & Kantola, 2019).

To meet these aims, RESISTIRÉ has conducted policy analysis, as well as quantitative and qualitative research activities, to inform the design of innovative solutions. In this way, it responded to the outbreak through co-created and inclusive strategies that addressed

old and new, durable and temporary inequality patterns in and across policy domains. The overall methodology of RESISTIRÉ is based on a step-by-step process running in three cycles over 30 months (April 2021/September 2023). All project activities were organised in these three cycles, feeding results into one another (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: RESISTIRÉ methodological step-by-step three-cycle process

This report provides an overview of the concrete outputs that were developed in all three cycles of the RESISTIRÉ project based on the results of the preceding research phases (WP2-4) and the Open Studios (WP5). These outputs have been variously targeted at different target groups, including policymakers, CSOs and NGOs, employers, educational stakeholders, the research community at large - including research funding organisations (RFOs) - and other stakeholders.

The outputs of the project were the results of three activities running in parallel. Firstly, there was the development of operational recommendations for different types of policymakers (national, regional, local levels) and other stakeholders (like CSOs and NGOs, employers, etc.) in the form of factsheets. In total, 22 different factsheets were created and promoted throughout the project. Secondly, certain ideas for potential pilot projects that came out of the Open Studios were further developed into more concrete specifications containing objectives, specific target groups, and expected impacts. In total, seven different concepts for pilot actions were finalised and launched, resulting in the implementation of nine pilots across Europe. Thirdly, the systematic monitoring of the analyses of quantitative and qualitative data in each cycle, as well as additional ideas

coming out of the Open Studios, contributed to the development of RESISTIRÉ's agendas for future research. Overall, a total of sixteen specific research agendas was released over the course of the project's three cycles.

In the next chapter, the processes of developing these three distinct outputs are described, with similarities and differences across cycles explored. The following chapter provides an overview of the results of these processes. The subsequent chapter describes the many lessons that were learned in the development of the operational recommendations, pilot projects, and future research agendas, followed by a chapter presenting overall conclusions.

Process

Operational Recommendations

This section describes the processes in T6.1 in all three cycles that produced and refined the 22 factsheets containing operational recommendations.

The development of the operational recommendations in the form of factsheets commenced in a similar manner in each cycle with the analysis of the results of the preceding research phases (WP2-4), more specifically of the identified issues and what solutions could counter them. In more concrete terms, task leader ISAS created a distinct document or Miro board in each cycle identifying shared themes that could be the focus of a factsheet. This analysis was then complemented by the results from the Open Studios in WP5, proposing additional topics that were considered for the factsheets. In identifying and further refining the recommendations, it was always deemed important to ensure that they had an innovative nature, that they could have a real and tangible impact, and that there was a balanced approach between different topics and target groups (both per cycle and across cycles).

In each cycle, first drafts were compiled of the proposed factsheets by designated leads and using a common preliminary structure to ensure a degree of consistency across the factsheets. This structure underwent some changes between the first and second cycles, with the third cycle adopting the same structure as used in the second cycle. Examples of these alterations include changing the 'background information' section for a 'problem statement' section and putting the actual recommendations at the beginning of the factsheet instead of at the end. The default structure used from the second cycle onwards included the following sections in order of appearance: a brief introduction, the recommendations themselves, the problem statement, relevant insights from RESISTIRÉ, a section dedicated to better stories, and three brief sections detailing the

RESISTIRÉ project, the authors and contributors to the factsheet and an acknowledgement and disclaimer. While most factsheets followed this structure, some were allowed to have a (slightly) different composition in order to strengthen their intended message.

To assess and refine these initial factsheets further, a workshop lasting approximately half a day was organised in each cycle that brought together consortium partners and external experts with specific expertise of the topics covered. For each of the factsheets, at least one external expert with specialised knowledge on the subject was recruited to participate. The workshop in the first cycle was organised online owing to the ongoing COVID-19 situation at the time, using a combination of Zoom and Miro to capture input. The two subsequent cycles saw workshops being organised in person, respectively in Prague and Gothenburg, using physical posters and sticky notes to capture the participants' feedback.

Every workshop was divided into two parts, with each part covering about half of the proposed factsheets per cycle and the participants working concurrently in three or four smaller groups. For each group, a previously designated moderator and note-taker helped facilitate the discussion and documentation of feedback. All participants received the factsheet drafts in advance of the workshop, but they were also able to reread them during their time in the small groups. The questions that were asked of them varied somewhat per cycle, but always included prompts about their initial spontaneous reactions to the recommendations, their thoughts about what the main message of the factsheet should be, whether any crucial information or elements were missing, and their considerations of what target groups the recommendations should address. Afterwards, participants shared their findings with the other groups in plenary to inform them and elicit any additional comments.

The feedback and input of the workshop participants were subsequently taken into account by the factsheet leads and supporting contributors, altering the documents where necessary and providing more in-depth recommendations. In the first cycle, for example, two of the initial factsheets were split, bringing the total number of factsheets to eight. Another example of a concrete change that resulted from this process was the merging of two proposed factsheets focusing on education in the second cycle, as this led to a clearer and more impactful factsheet.

After the drafting of new versions of the factsheets by the leads and contributors, a review of the contents of each document was carried out by task leader ISAS in each cycle. Subsequently, the documents were edited based on these reviews, and the other consortium partners were able to leave their feedback as well. Some of the factsheets were also sent to the external experts who had participated in one of the workshops to ask for additional comments. Integrating all of this feedback, the factsheets were then

finalised and proofread to ensure their readiness for communication and dissemination to the identified target groups.

Moreover, the documents were strengthened through the use of visual materials (i.e., infographics). This is important as visuals create ‘hooks’ throughout the text that keep readers engaged throughout the document. They also help readers to see beyond just the statistics and look at the actual impacts of policies/inequalities, as well as communicate key messages without the use of words: even if a reader casually peruses the document, a few key messages will ideally stick in their minds. Therefore, each factsheet went through a process of identifying the most appropriate messages/content for visualisation and, subsequently, developing and integrating those visuals. Visual metaphors were often used to communicate complex topics or themes: simple, symbolic images can quickly tell a story in a way that is easy to interpret and, ideally, triggers the reader to pay (more) attention. Another method that was utilised was the use of contrast. Inequalities, for example, can be visually communicated by comparing privileged and vulnerable situations side-by-side, thus emphasising the injustice and (growing) divide. In the case of D6.1, the visuals were ready in time to be included in the report, while they were not included in either D6.2 or D6.3 due to time constraints.

Pilot Projects

This section describes the processes in T6.2 in the first two cycles that resulted in the formulation of terms of reference for the pilot projects that RESISTIRÉ launched.

A total of 45 distinct action-ideas came out of the first and second cycles of Open Studios that had the potential to be further developed into full-fledged pilot projects. Out of these, a selection of the most promising action-ideas was made, based on the following criteria:

- The innovative nature of the action;
- The potential impact of the action;
- The potential of the action to attract attention and awareness;
- The practical feasibility of the action, including for example the estimated budget, the possibility of finding an organisation to carry out the project, etc.

The process for creating a first shortlist and selecting the final action-ideas for development as pilot projects differed between the two cycles, with YW leading a deliberation effort among the consortium in the first cycle. The twenty action-ideas that had come out of the first-cycle Open Studios - i.e., one-page descriptions per idea, outlining their focus, target audience, objectives, and important actions that would need to be undertaken if implemented - were evaluated, on the basis of which a YW-proposed shortlist was shared with K&I (as task leader) and SU (as they had been strongly involved

with the Open Studios). This shortlist of five potential pilot projects was agreed upon and further developed before being shared with the wider consortium for feedback. Consortium partners were able to add crucial information – such as relevant organisations that could carry out the projects – and express their interest in leading or contributing to the design of the projects. At the end of this process, three action-ideas received the most support from the consortium to be developed further: Caring Workspaces, Employers Who Care, and Green Spaces as Ecosystems of Care.

Based on the interest expressed before, leads were appointed to develop each of the chosen actions into concrete terms of reference. They were supported throughout the development process by a core group of contributors from the consortium partners. K&I and YW, as WP task leader and WP leader respectively, were part of all three core groups. K&I also developed a template for the terms of reference to be used by all groups, containing standard parts and customisable parts. This template (also used in the second cycle) consisted of the following sections, which could be adapted as necessary: technical specifications (expected tasks and work plan), who can apply and what skills are required, how to apply, the evaluation process, the external monitoring process, the available budget and financial conditions, the timing of the call, support to applicants, awarding organisation (administrative tasks and obligations), and a list of eligible costs (in an annex).

Once the focus, target, objectives, and actions required to implement each pilot project had been clearly defined, the drafting teams integrated these into the template. When the first drafts of the terms of reference were finalised, they were tested with at least one organisation (up to three in some cases) knowledgeable on the subject. This allowed the researchers to obtain feedback from organisations that could be involved and to obtain their opinions on the feasibility of the action, on what needed to be clarified or modified, and on alternative specifications. In parallel, a template for the application form for submitting proposals was also developed by K&I and, where necessary, adapted to the specifications of each pilot project. This template was part of the documents accompanying the calls for proposals and was designed to guide potential applicants in the presentation of their project proposals. It was also used in the second cycle.

As for the second cycle selection process and drafting, YW and K&I created a shortlist of potential pilot projects by dividing the available action-ideas that had come out of the Open Studios into three distinct categories, based on their overall feasibility, innovativeness, and potential for impact: promising pilot projects, feasible pilot projects (but with lower innovativeness), and ambitious pilot projects (potentially beyond RESISTIRÉ's capabilities). Based on this categorisation, a shortlist was eventually established, with nine out of 25 ideas being selected for further deliberation and desk research. This desk research was carried out by YW and K&I and included finding out whether projects similar to the proposed ideas had already been carried out (in a

European context) and what potential organisations could be approached to execute the ideas. Subsequently, these nine potential pilot projects - which corresponded to the two main themes of the second-cycle Open Studios - were presented to the wider consortium. After a democratic voting process, four ideas were selected for further development: two education-based projects (Care Fair and Inclusive Schools) and two GBV-related projects (Engaging with Gender-based Violence Through Sports and We Will Survive Secondary Trauma)

The development process after selection was similar to that of the first cycle. Separate meetings for each of the four selected projects were organised and interested consortium partners were invited to attend. During these meetings, the focus of the pilot projects (i.e., in terms of target groups, concrete steps, etc.) was defined further, and leads and contributors were appointed. Testing of the drafts was once again carried out with external organisations.

For both cycles - after the terms of reference and the application form were finalised - public calls were issued on the RESISTIRÉ website and disseminated through social media platforms, the project website, and the consortium partners' professional networks. The evaluation of submitted proposals happened in two steps. Firstly, evaluators that were involved in drafting the pilot projects' terms of reference were appointed per pilot project to assess the proposals on the basis of an evaluation template with quantitative and qualitative sections. Subsequently, the three proposals with the highest scores were shortlisted³ (based on the sum and average of the scores assigned to the identified criteria) and a jury was set up to interview the teams/coordinators behind these proposals. This jury consisted of the WP task leader, the WP leader, and the partner coordinating the development of the terms of reference. The jury panel held a Q&A session on the projects' strengths and weaknesses via video call with the shortlisted applicants (per pilot project), which ultimately led to the selection of one proposal to be funded by RESISTIRÉ (or two, in the case of Green Spaces as Ecosystems of Care and Engaging with Gender-based Violence Through Sports). The monitoring and evaluation of these projects was carried out under T6.5 and is outside the purview of this report.

Agendas for Future Research

This section describes the processes in T6.3 in all three cycles that produced the sixteen RESISTIRÉ research agendas intended for dissemination and promotion among

³ In the two cases where less than three proposals were received that passed the minimum score (Care Fair and Inclusive Schools), the qualifying proposals were immediately shortlisted for the interview.

research funding organisations.

The findings produced by RESISTIRÉ's research phases are based on the analysis of various empirical data collected and analysed in WP2-4: the mapping of policies and societal initiatives, official secondary data sources at the international and EU level as well as RAS at the national level, expert interviews and workshops, and narratives from people belonging to vulnerable groups. In the various research agendas, these findings were analysed in order to identify what knowledge is still missing. This way, further research directions were identified that are aimed at improving the development and implementation of pandemic-induced policies/responses (now and in the future), considering their impacts on vulnerable groups and (pre-)existing inequalities.

The development of research agendas followed a similar approach to the one used for the operational recommendations, which is described above. In a first step, the WP leaders of WP2, WP3 and WP4 identified initial knowledge gaps and research questions to be pursued based on the results of WP2-4. Insights from the Open Studios were added in this process as well. Afterwards, task leader ORU/UGOT summarised these results and circulated initial drafts of research agendas among the consortium (four RAs in the first cycle and six RAs each in the second and third cycles). For each proposed research agenda, a lead and team were selected from among the consortium partners (who had expressed an interest to contribute) to further develop the document. These drafts followed a format emphasising knowledge gaps and research questions, and served as the foundation for a consortium workshop as well as a process of further development and finalisation after the workshop. There were two main differences compared with the process for operational recommendations: the Open Studios generally provided more input for the factsheets and the workshop participants were solely members of the consortium; no external experts were involved in this process.

The workshop of the first cycle was held online due to the ongoing COVID-19 situation at the time. Participants split into breakout groups, where they (re)read the drafts and reflected on the knowledge gaps and research questions. Afterwards, the drafts were finalised by task leader ORU and WP leader YW.

The workshop of the second cycle was held in Prague and followed a 'World Café' approach (Brown & Isaacs, 1995) with the following characteristics:

- Each research agenda topic had a table where the lead author of the agenda acted as host;
- Participants switched tables every twenty minutes, allowing everyone to contribute to all topics;
- Once participants arrived at a table, they were briefed on inputs from previous participants by the table host and built further on the formulated research questions.

Results were presented in plenary and also led to a discussion on the focus of research activities for RESISTIRÉ’s third cycle. The latter was complemented by advice from the RESISTIRÉ Advisory Board meeting that was held shortly thereafter.

The workshop of the third cycle was organised in Gothenburg. The consortium partners received access to the six research agenda drafts before the workshop and, during the workshop in small groups, were able to (re)read these documents. After everyone had familiarised themselves with the documents, they reflected on the knowledge gaps/research questions that were already included, as well as any dimensions that might be missing. Afterwards, the results were presented in plenary.

Following the workshops in both the second and third cycles, the twelve research agendas (six per cycle) were revised by the leads of each research agenda, collectively reviewed by the partners in the task, and finalised by the task leader. The final drafts were quality reviewed by the consortium.

Results – Operational Recommendations

The 22 factsheets with operational recommendations that were developed in RESISTIRÉ are listed in the table below. They can be accessed on the [project website](#), or directly through the links in the table.

Table 1 - Operational Recommendations

Cycle	No.	Title	Target Group(s)
1	1	Pandemic and Gender Mainstreaming. Decades of work towards intersectional gender mainstreaming wiped out during the crisis!	Policy makers
1	2	Ensuring gender-balanced decision-making and the involvement of civil society	Policy makers and CSOs
1	3	Gender Equality Plans should be mandatory for hospitals	Employers (hospitals) and policy makers
1	4	Green for Everyone. Promoting Green Spaces and Mitigating Gentrification	Policy makers, CSOs and employers
1	5	Care and Crisis: Fostering a Paradigm Shift	Employers and policy makers
1	6A	Reinforcing EU level action to combat gender-based violence through the Istanbul Convention	Policy makers

1	6B	Improving national responses to gender-based violence: lessons from the pandemic crisis	Policy makers
1	7	Telework as a Double-edged Sword: Risks and Opportunities	Employers and policy makers
2	8	Crisis Management for All: Inclusive, Multi-actor Crisis Management	Policy makers
2	9	Gender-based Violence During Crises: Risk Assessment, Prevention and Effective Response	Policy makers and key stakeholders like the police, social services, and CSOs
2	10	Creating Safe Digital Spaces	Policy makers, tech and social media companies, education stakeholders, employers
2	11	Education: Developing Resilient Education Systems	Education stakeholders (i.e., schools, parents, teachers, associations), policy makers, CSOs
2	12	The Missing Perspectives of Women in the National Recovery and Resilience Plans	Policy makers
2	13	Striving for Social Justice: Vulnerable Groups in the Recovery Policies	Policy makers
3	14	Mental Health Support in Times of Crisis	Policy makers, employers, education stakeholders, medical practitioners
3	15	Access to Health Services for Vulnerable Groups	Public health policy makers, CSOs, activists, equality bodies
3	16	Digital Transformation for an Inclusive Post-COVID Recovery	Policy makers (members of the European Commission for 'A Europe Fit for the Digital Age'), CSOs
3	17	Promoting Sustainable and Resilient Long-Term Care	Policy makers, care service providers, activists
3	18	Approaching the Crisis as a Continuum: Learning from an Inclusive Feminist Crisis Response	Policy makers, CSOs, activists
3	19	Transformative Funding: A Pathway for Creative and Effective Crisis Response	Funding organisations
3	20	More Intersectional Data	Policy makers, European-level statistics bodies
3	21	Addressing Poverty and Social Exclusion: A Feminist Perspective	Policy makers, street-level bureaucrats, CSOs

Results – Pilot Projects

The seven pilot project concepts for which terms of reference were developed in RESISTIRÉ are briefly described below. Table 2 provides an overview of the pilot projects. While seven concepts were developed, a total of nine pilot projects was actually implemented (in eight different countries), as two proposals were selected for both Green Spaces as Ecosystems of Care and Engaging with Gender-based Violence Through Sports. Information on the implemented pilot projects is available on the [project website](#).

Table 2 - Pilot Projects

Cycle	Pilot Project	Implementing organisation	Country
1	Employers Who Care	SOS Racismo	Spain
1	Green Spaces as Ecosystems of Care	Transition Graz	Austria
1	Green Spaces as Ecosystems of Care	aquí	Spain
1	Caring Workspaces	Postane	Turkey
2	Care Fair - A School-based Wellbeing Event	Nevypust' duši	Czechia
2	Inclusive Schools - A Toolbox to Engage All Parents and Guardians in Dialogue	Romedia	Hungary
2	Engaging with Gender-based Violence Through Sports	Atina	Serbia
2	Engaging with Gender-based Violence Through Sports	Altis and Panteion University	Greece
2	Exhale: Moving Through Secondary Trauma Together	Chayn	UK

All projects were implemented, and the results of the Monitoring and Evaluation of the projects can be found in D6.5. The objectives pursued by each of the projects is briefly described below, with a link to the project description on the RESISTIRÉ project website.

Allied Employers (Employers Who Care) - SOS Racismo

Allied Employers aimed at creating a meeting space between migrant domestic workers and employers, to reflect on the needs of both parties and draft viable proposals together to ensure quality care and decent conditions for workers, employers and cared-for people. The pilot also aimed at raising awareness among employers and the general public about the inequalities of this sector and the future of care, through visual material.

Green Spaces as Ecosystems of Care

RESISTIRÉ supported two pilot projects transforming green spaces into 'Ecosystems of Care' through the development and implementation of programmes that make all users,

and in particular vulnerable groups, feel welcome and able to access green spaces.

[Transition Graz](#)

The 'Ecosystems of Care' pilot project in Austria was run by a consortium of two organisations. Transition Graz is an association that is committed to transitioning to a more socially just society and aims to connect sustainable, regenerative urban development with 'traditional' social and community work. They were supported in this effort by their field partner Illusions, which runs a community development / neighbourhood centre in the target area of the pilot project. This area was the Triester Neighbourhood, a multi-ethnic low-income area in the south of the city of Graz. Two green areas in the neighbourhood were used for the project. A programme of activities was co-developed with users, to cover unmet needs and to increase the use of the green spaces by people who were underutilising them; these were mainly girls and women. Although the project faced challenges, it managed to have the expected impact and to become sustainable. The city of Graz is also investing in the two green areas to facilitate this more diverse use by new groups of people.

[aquí](#)

aquí is a social innovation collective based in Barcelona. The green space they covered was the Parc de l'Espanya Industrial, in the centre of the city of Barcelona. This park is heavily used, which leads to conflicts between users and neighbours of the park. Through action research and co-creation, the project developed a diversity of new activities, involving both users and non-users of the park. This brought very different people together like people from the queer community, healthcare workers, the local basketball association, and the group of skateboarders active in the park. New activities brought into this park have a strong gender inclusion component and included free cinefora (with debates) and regular capoeira sessions.

[Caring Workspaces](#) - Postane

This pilot project was implemented by Postane and Hafiza Merkezi and aimed to create workspaces that are inclusive, diverse, safe and caring for employees. The focus was on workers and employers in the fields of civil society and social good. Both organisations are based in Turkey, and the project was implemented at European and national level (in English and Turkish). After performing research (collecting better stories, conducting a survey), a checklist was developed as an instrument for organisations to check whether their workspace is indeed caring. The final activity was an open call for the "Better story of caring workplaces" award, launched and advertised on social media. Eighteen applications for the award were formally submitted following the pre-selection process (twelve from Turkey and four from other countries). A survey was consequently distributed to the employees of these organisations and five were then selected for the public vote. The checklist created by the project can be replicated and scaled up in other contexts outside of the CSO environment (e.g., corporate employers) and replicated in

other national and regional contexts.

Care Fair - A school-based wellbeing event - *Nevypust' duši*

The overall objective of this pilot project was to empower 15- to 18-year-olds to take ownership of their wellbeing, including but not limited to mental, emotional, psychological, sexual, reproductive, social, and community health. By connecting students with organisations/NGOs/experts active in the context of wellbeing, they would gain a better understanding of the resources available to them and their access rights. After a first informal contact at the fair, this would reduce the barrier to seek help or to start taking preventive measures. More specifically, the pilot project aimed to:

- Raise awareness among the student population about the importance of a holistic understanding of wellbeing.
- Expand access to knowledge and resources for prevention, care, and self-care among students.
- Foster a dialogue among students about these issues.
- Give students the possibility to actively engage in the implementation of a project, outside the teaching programme.

Inclusive schools: Engaging Parents of Vulnerable Youth - *Romedia Foundation*

This pilot project led by Romedia Foundation aimed to:

- Gather the most up-to-date information about the challenges, best practices, and regional particularities related to Hungarian schools' engagements with Roma parents;
- Identify existing strategies and forms of engagement between Roma parents and schools;
- Prepare a Toolbox with best practices ("better stories") and resources for schools to efficiently engage with hard-to-reach parents.

Engaging with Gender-based Violence Through Sports

Sports can be a key tool for promoting positive social and personal values, such as team spirit, discipline, perseverance and fair play. However, if poorly designed or managed, sports activities can reinforce (gender) stereotypes, heteronormativity and male dominance, as well as reinforce attitudes and behaviour of exclusion or violence. In fact, gender-based violence is still widespread in sports clubs, although it is under-reported. Two projects were funded to test approaches to use sports and sports clubs to empower young people against gender-based violence. Non-formal education techniques were used by both projects, training coaches to use these techniques during their sports trainings, sports camps and other activities. Both projects also organised an event as part of the project - a festival - where young athletes could experience and share.

ATINA

This project was implemented in southern Serbia, a region near the borders of Kosovo and Northern Macedonia, with large refugee camps. Eight different sports clubs and a school were involved in the activities.

ALTIS

This project was organised in Athens where Altis is active as a sports club. The Centre for Gender Studies at Panteion University was also associated with the project. The final event was the Katatopia Festival, a sports event organised by Panteion University annually for its students, where innovative sports games are played that create awareness and counter typical heteronormative stereotypes. Through the project, this festival was opened to involve the young athletes from ALTIS and other sports clubs.

Exhale: Moving Through Secondary Trauma Together - Chayn

Secondary trauma occurs when an individual is told about or otherwise exposed to another person's trauma, and is an acute risk across caring professions, policy, advocacy, and other practitioners who work with survivors of gender-based violence. The effects of secondary trauma on mental health are often dismissed, belittled, or stigmatised, and burnout and compassion fatigue are rife. Many services lack adequate infrastructure and resourcing for team support, leaving practitioners, activists, and other professionals in this space unwilling or unable to access mental health support. This leads to high turnover and under-resourcing of the sector, and thus reduced quality of support for survivors. Preventing and mitigating secondary trauma requires structural support and a supportive workplace environment. The programme has been delivered to a 'community of practice' of practitioners in Europe-based organisations who work with survivors of gender-based violence, in particular technology-facilitated abuse. The aims of this programme are to inform, support, and connect, thereby validating the experiences of the community of practice, and empowering them to adopt supportive team practices in their own organisations. While taking part in the programme, the community of practice acquired skills for managing and preventing secondary trauma, and built skills, knowledge, and solidarity with a network of peers and partners across Europe.

Results – Agendas for Future Research

The sixteen research agendas that were developed in RESISTIRÉ can be accessed through the [project website](#). They are listed in Table 3 below.

Table 3 - Agendas for Future Research

Cycle	Research Agenda - thematic focus
1	Care
1	Work and Pay
1	Human Rights and Health
1	Gender-based Violence
2	Inclusive Recovery
2	Intersectional Data Collection and Analysis
2	Care
2	Work and Employment
2	Education
2	Gender-based Violence
3	Health Inequalities
3	Inequalities in Age and Ageing
3	Digitalisation
3	Gender+ Inclusive Green Spaces
3	Civic Responses to Crisis
3	Gender-based Violence

As indicated in the table, the research agendas are integrated in reports for each cycle. The [first cycle report](#) covered four domains, while the [second cycle report](#) had somewhat similar contents (RAs on Care, Work and Employment and Gender-based Violence) and covered six domains in total. Finally, the [third cycle report](#) outlined research questions and topics that future research should address in six distinct areas.

Lessons Learned

Operational Recommendations

This section highlights the lessons learned from the process carried out in Task 6.1, creating operational recommendations on the basis of the results from the preceding research phases and the outputs from the Open Studios. In total, 22 RESISTIRÉ factsheets were successfully developed, released and disseminated as a result of this task. Nevertheless, the research methodology applied in this project encompassed some challenges that needed to be overcome. The lessons learned from these challenges are detailed below.

The first challenge was the need to provide fast results in a context of rapid change. In an attempt to adequately respond to the rapidly changing situation concerning the

COVID-19 pandemic, the data collection process was divided into three fast-paced research cycles addressing a broad variety of topics. While this rapid research approach allowed for a quick gathering of answers to the most pressing issues arising from different phases of the pandemic, it also limited the consortium's capacity to conduct a detailed, in-depth analysis of the problem. As a consequence, the operational outcomes produced on the basis of the RESISTIRÉ research findings are not exhaustive and could most certainly be enriched by further investigations.

The second challenge consisted of the fact that results from multiple methods had to be integrated, which led to an oversupply of data. The multi-method approach incorporating the parallel collection of different types of data provided a multidimensional understanding of the societal challenges the project had been facing on the one hand, but the plethora of data could also not be fully exploited due to the relatively short duration of the project on the other hand.

The third and final challenge consisted of utilising an EU-wide scope. In this regard, the cross-national analysis conducted by RESISTIRÉ presented some challenges. The risk of trying to formulate general European-level policy recommendations without taking into account differing national contexts (e.g., the quality of democracy, ideology of the ruling party, etc.) was that the proposed solutions could end up not reaching significant detail and depth. However, RESISTIRÉ endeavoured to circumvent problems of this kind, relying on the experience of each consortium partner to adopt an advocacy plan for the promotion of the policy guidelines that fit the specific national context.

Pilot Projects

This section highlights the lessons learned from the process carried out in Task 6.2, which had the ambitious objective of both transforming a selection of action-ideas from the Open Studios into well-structured calls for proposals for the implementation of pilot projects as well as the selection of CSOs capable of making them a reality. Although clear and ambitious, the process put in place during the two cycles, which was largely designed from scratch, ran smoothly and allowed for the launch of a larger number of calls than foreseen in the Grant Agreement (three instead of two in the first cycle and four instead of two in the second cycle). The following are some of the key lessons learnt from the process.

First of all, the ideas for pilot projects, as they came out of the Open Studios, were described in a schematic and concise document and shared with the consortium. This proved an effective method of providing sufficient information to the project partners, even to people who had not attended the Open Studio and had no further insight into

the discussions that took place. The democratic voting process, whereby the consortium selects a limited number of ideas to develop further, went smoothly in RESISTIRÉ, but it could also result in a more balanced distribution of preferences (i.e., no clear winners). In case of the latter, a second round of voting might be necessary.

The task leader also learned that it was useful to create a template for the call for proposals, consisting of a standard part and a customisable part, so that the draft leads and contributors could follow a pre-defined structure when developing the documents. This also makes sure that the many aspects involved in the implementation of a pilot project are covered and makes it clearer to applicants what is expected of them. Nevertheless, it also proved essential to include an e-mail address in the call for proposals, so that applicants could request assistance and clear up any doubts they might have. Tests are an essential part of the call development process as well, as they allow the perspectives of potential applicants to be incorporated into the technical specifications.

Similarly, the task leader learned that keeping the application form for submitting proposals relatively simple, with a few questions to be answered and a clear word limit, allowed the subsequent evaluation process to run smoothly and quickly. With regard to the receiving of proposals, it became clear that this is quite dependent on the timeframe and the time of year that the calls are opened and promoted: the fewest applications are likely to be received if the call is launched and promoted in the summer period (as was the case in the second cycle) and is open for less than three weeks. Conversely, the highest number of applications is likely to be received if the call is launched in autumn/winter/spring (as in the first cycle) and is open for at least a month.

In terms of facilitating the work of the jury members during the evaluation process, it is important to prepare a guide for them and to send them specific e-mails before the start of the evaluation as regular reminders. The evaluation template that was compiled and distributed to the evaluators beforehand also proved to be beneficial to the effectiveness and swiftness with which this process was conducted. Finally, as several applicants asked after the evaluation process to understand why their proposal had not been shortlisted or selected for funding, a feedback report template could also be created to provide feedback to them - either all candidates or those that explicitly ask for it.

Agendas for Future Research

This section highlights the lessons learned from the process carried out in Task 6.3, which developed agendas for future research. The aim of the research agendas in the project was to identify knowledge gaps and formulate future research needs to understand, address, and mitigate behavioural, social, and economic inequalities

produced by the policy and societal responses to COVID-19. RESISTIRÉ is a project designed to provide rapid results working in the uncertain and ever-changing context of a global crisis, the pandemic. In several ways, the overall structure and design of the project enabled and enriched the proposed agendas for future research. In total, sixteen thematic research agendas were developed (Živković et al., 2022; Sandström & Strid, 2022; Sandström, Callerstig & Strid, 2023), disseminated and promoted.

Crucially, involving a diverse range of actors in the research process (i.e., researchers, civil society, individuals affected by COVID-19-related policies, public authorities) enabled the project to identify knowledge gaps that may not have been immediately obvious within the scientific community and, furthermore, the research agendas produced have been discussed with different stakeholders in webinars organised after their completion.

The combined efforts of a consortium of multidisciplinary partners, from different fields of expertise and with different theoretical and methodological perspectives, provided a rich foundation of materials on which to base the research agendas. However, this richness also led to some challenges. Firstly, in terms of defining the scope of the research agendas, there was at times a certain degree of uncertainty whether the research agendas should focus on broad research areas or specific research questions. This first option risked being too general and superficial, while the second risked being too narrow and context dependent. As such, this point also ties in with the point below about the potential benefits of national research agendas.

Secondly, as a wealth of research results were produced within the project itself, the research agendas were primarily based upon these findings. However, this was done with the risk of neglecting previous and ongoing research elsewhere. The inclusion of a more thorough review of existing research in light of the specific project results would have been desirable, but in that case, more time would have had to be allocated to review research. Thirdly, in retrospect, the resources within the project could have been used more efficiently through better alignment between the operational recommendations (Task 6.1) and the research agendas (Task 6.3). They could have been harmonised in terms of themes which would have allowed for a shared review of the results and other, external, research results. At times, Tasks 6.1 and 6.3 seemed like two competing rather than complimentary tasks.

Finally, a major lesson learnt relates to the identification and the definition of stakeholders/target groups, where - in the context of multi-European partner collaborations - it is particularly important to consider:

- National variations between research funders and their respective remits, as stipulated by national regulations, e.g., the extent to which research funding organisations can shift funding into new, emerging, themes or not, and at what

pace; at short notice or in the long term.

- National context and the positioning of, in the case of RESISTIRÉ, gender+ inequalities in the national policy work.
- Thematic research areas funded: whether research funding organisations are already limited by focusing on specific thematic areas, or if they fund basic/ground research.
- Private or public funding body: whether the research funding organisation is privately or publicly funded. This makes a difference to their ability and willingness to engage in new, sometimes risky, research themes.

To address these issues, lessons learnt are to:

- Include a mapping of research funding organisations on the national level, including the variables outlined above.
- Potentially focus on EU-level funders, at the expense of national research funding organisations, as this enables a more specific and dedicated formulation of the research agenda.
- Design the research agendas so that each consortium partner takes responsibility to develop a national (country-specific) research agenda, relevant to the specific national research funding context.

Despite a wealth of research and evidence on how COVID-19 and its policy and societal responses have increased, created new, and sometimes mitigated and reduced gender+ inequalities, major knowledge gaps remain. Some of these have been identified in the research agendas of the three cycles of RESISTIRÉ. Some of these inequalities have been in focus in much pandemic research, while others have not. The research agendas show that there is still an overwhelming need for empirical research on the impact of the pandemic from the perspective of the gender+ and inequality domains lens applied in RESISTIRÉ. The required empirical research concerns both more basic research to better understand the effects of the pandemic and more applied research, i.e., seeking practical applications for the research results obtained, directed towards specific practical aims or objectives.

Another important lesson learnt concerns the need to broaden the research on the pandemic in order to understand better 'what works' and 'what needs to change and how'. Much of the pandemic research has focused on the negative effects of the pandemic, but significantly less attention has been paid to the counter-stories and 'better stories' of the pandemic. Such counter-stories can include individual and organisational agency, actions and practices, as well as actions and practices of inclusive feminist solidarity and support, that may mitigate inequalities and strengthen the resilience of individuals, organisations, and societies. Counter-stories to the dominant narrative include actions and inspiring practices to cope with the pandemic, giving voice to otherwise less visible and marginalised groups. Better stories are those that challenge

the dominant narrative and are inclusive and representative of marginalised communities. Hence, they have the potential to challenge established orders, truths, and power structures. Dominant narratives often exclude and marginalise certain groups of people, but by re-telling stories that are more inclusive and representative of marginalised communities, these dominant narratives can be disrupted, and the analysis can contribute to the creation of more equitable and just societies. A research focus on better stories is therefore important in understanding the transition out of social exclusion and marginalisation and in supporting the ability to act and have an impact on society.

Conclusions

This report provides an overview of the operational recommendations, pilot actions, and research agendas that have been developed as part of the WP6 activities across all cycles, as well as lessons learnt from developing them. Concretely, the output consists of 22 operational recommendations, seven pilot project concepts, and sixteen thematic research agendas. The production of these outputs has followed different processes depending on the associated task, but they have all worked well throughout the three cycles of the project. The lessons learned provide an opportunity to utilise and improve these processes to facilitate solution development in future projects and/or other contexts.

Some reflections and conclusions relating to the overall research process in RESISTIRÉ, which directly affected the different types of solutions presented in this report, are as follows. Due to the rapid and uncertain nature of the pandemic and how it unfolded, one of the conclusions that was made early on was the need for innovative research methods that could be used in this exceptional situation. In particular, the research process in the project benefited from an abductive approach, using a set of open-ended questions and the application of a broad theoretical framework as the main theoretical approach. This approach has meant gathering empirical data while simultaneously providing input for the development of the theoretical framework in a way which allows for the further refinement of existing questions and for the formulation of new questions in the following cycles. In this way an interplay and exchange between empirical data and theory have been achieved throughout the project. This has enabled what has been called “systematic combining”, meaning the matching of theory with empirical findings that inform the directions and re-directions throughout the course of the project (Dubois & Gadde, 2002).

The research process has to a large extent been bottom-up and interactive, and the results have been collected, analysed and validated with the help of inequality experts

from civil society, public authorities, academia, and from individual people throughout Europe sharing their professional knowledge and personal experiences of life during COVID-19. In the three cycles, different groups of informants were invited to provide input related to their knowledge and experiences of inequalities during the pandemic and input on how to interpret and address those experiences. The collaborative and interactive approach has been a process of validation, but also essential in the way that practitioners have contributed with a complex, practical, and contextual understanding to the researchers' more theoretical and generic understanding. Concrete examples of these interactions were the workshops, but also the collection of narratives, which are important means for marginalised groups to be heard in a way that emphasises their own voices and agency and can furthermore serve as a "consciousness-raising tool" (Gunnarsson, 2006).

The Open Studios are an integral part of the RESISTIRÉ methodology, a vital participatory extension of the research approach applied in the project. The interactive and participatory approach has also been important for this step where the Open Studios seek to facilitate a process of joint analysis, learning together and the co-creation of solutions to be tested practically and, as a result, contributing to the "elusive recipe for successful gender equality policy" (Engeli & Mazur, 2018: 112). One of the overall results from RESISTIRÉ thus relates to its approach, which we see as a fruitful way of developing a more robust understanding of complex societal inequalities in particular contexts, while at the same time having a strong potential to contribute to developing and testing responses to these challenges.

Before concluding with reflections on the three types of solutions developed by RESISTIRÉ, an essential consideration to take into account is the importance of national contexts and variations. While some of the operational recommendations were targeted at the EU level, others were intended for advocacy on the national, regional or local level. This posed a challenge, as specific geographical contexts could only be accounted for in a limited way during the formulation of the factsheets which, in turn, complicated advocacy on the national level (or lower). This caveat also applies to the implementation of the pilot projects, as the national, regional and/or local context could differ substantially between selected pilot projects and have a significant influence on the practical implementation of their programme, as well as on their potential for replicability and scalability.

The factsheets highlight various issues that became apparent through the research and co-creation phases and offer operational recommendations to counter negative developments and ameliorate situations that arose as a result of the pandemic. While the factsheets of the first cycle cover a variety of topics like GBV, gender mainstreaming, and care (among others), the second cycle factsheets by and large highlighted the importance of institutional crisis preparedness and resilience, as well as a fair and

inclusive recovery. The latter is especially pertinent when looking at the project's gender+ analysis of the various NRRPs' proposed measures. Several of the third-cycle factsheets, meanwhile, continue to emphasise competent crisis management as well as the importance of health and care services during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic.

The number and quality of potential pilot projects that came out of the Open Studios was far more than the project could handle, making the choice of projects to be further developed and, subsequently, launched extremely challenging for the consortium. Eventually, a total of seven pilot project concepts were developed and launched, surpassing the original number planned. These can be broadly categorised in three different categories, i.e., pilot projects related to care and community (in the workplace, in green spaces), to education, and to ways to counter (the effects of) gender-based violence.

Finally, with regard to the research agendas, the first cycle posed some initial research questions based on knowledge gaps in the care, human rights and health, work and pay, and GBV domains. The second cycle subsequently sought to provide answers to some of the first cycle's questions, but also produced a range of research agendas of its own, focusing on GBV, care, work and employment, education, inclusive recovery, and intersectional data collection and analysis. The third cycle built further on some of the earlier research agendas and looked at some domains that were previously not taken up, covering the themes of GBV, health inequalities, inequalities in age and ageing, digitalisation, gender+ inclusive green spaces, and civic responses to crisis. These knowledge gaps and research questions were promoted towards research funding organisations in order to ensure that innovative research is carried out across Europe beyond the duration of the RESISTIRÉ project.

References

Axelsson, T. K., Callerstig, A-C., Sandström, L., & Strid, S. (2021). *RESISTIRE D4.1 Qualitative indications of inequalities produced by COVID-19 and its policy responses. 1st cycle summary report*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5595815>.

Bonaccorsi, G., Pierri, F., Cinelli, M., Porcelli, F., Galeazzi, A., Flori, A., & Pammolli, F. (2020). Economic and social consequences of human mobility restrictions under COVID-19. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 117(27), 15530-15535. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2007658117>.

Brown, J., & Isaacs, D. (1995). *The World Cafe Book. Shaping Our Futures Through Conversations that Matter*. San Fransisco: Berrett-Kohler Publishers.

<http://theworldcafe.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/sofdownload1.pdf>.

Cibin, R., Stöckelová, T., & Linková, M. (2021). *RESISTIRE D2.1 - Summary Report mapping cycle 1*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5361042>.

Cibin, R., Ghidoni, E., Aristegui-Fradua, I. E., Marañon, U. B., Stöckelová, T., & Linková, M. (2022). *RESISTIRE D2.2 Summary report on mapping cycle 2*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6536060>.

Cibin, R., Ghidoni, E., Stöckelová, T., & Linková, M. (2023). *RESISTIRE D2.3 Summary report mapping cycle 3*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7708631>.

Cumming, C., Wood, L., & Davies, A. (2020). People experiencing homelessness urgently need to be recognised as a high-risk group for COVID-19. *Health Promotion Journal of Australia*. Wiley & Sons Inc.

Dubois, A., & Gadde, L-E. (2002). Systematic combining: an abductive approach to case research. *Journal of Business Research*, 55(7), 553-560. DOI:10.1016/S0148-2963(00)00195-8.

Engeli, I., & Mazur, A. (2018). Taking implementation seriously in assessing success: The politics of gender equality policy. *European Journal of Politics and Gender*, 1(1-2), 111-129. <https://doi.org/10.1332/251510818X15282097548558>.

Gunnarsson, E. (2006). The snake and the apple in the common paradise. In K. Aagard Nielsen & L. Svensson (eds.). (2006). *Action research and interactive research. Beyond practice and theory*. Maastricht: Shaker publishing.

Lewnard, J. A., & Lo, N. C. (2020). Scientific and ethical basis for social-distancing interventions against COVID-19. *The Lancet. Infectious disease*.

Lokot, M., & Avakyan, Y. (2020). Intersectionality as a lens to the COVID-19 pandemic: implications for sexual and reproductive health in development and humanitarian contexts. *Sexual and Reproductive Health Matters*, 28:1.

Lombardo, E., & Kantola, J. (2019). European integration and disintegration: Feminist perspectives on inequalities and social justice. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 57(S1), 62-76.

Nicola, M., Alsafi, Z., Sohrabi, C., Kerwan, A., Al-Jabir, A., Iosifidis, C., & Agha, R. (2020). The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus and COVID-19 pandemic: a review. *International Journal of Surgery*, 78, 185-193.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijisu.2020.04.018>.

Sandström, L., & Strid, S. (2022). *RESISTIRE Agenda for Future Research - cycle 2*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7043345>.

Sandström, L., Axelsson, T. K., Callerstig, A.-C., Strid, S., & Bobek, A. (2022). *RESISTIRE D4.2 Building back better? Qualitative indications of inequalities produced by Covid-19 and its policy and societal responses. Second cycle summary report*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6517795>.

Sandström, L., Callerstig, A.-C., & Strid, S. (2023). *RESISTIRÉ Agenda for future research. Addressing the impacts of Covid-19 policies on gendered inequalities - cycle 3*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.811439>

Sandström, L., Callerstig, A.-C., Strid, S., Lionello, L., & Rossetti, F. (2023). *RESISTIRE D4.3 Summary report on qualitative indicators - cycle 3*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7708724>.

Sciensano. (2020). *COVID-19 Epidemiologische situatie*.

Van Bavel, J. J., Baicker, K., Boggio, P. S., Capraro, V., Cichocka, A., Cikara, M., Crockett, M. J., Crum, A. J., Douglas, K. M., Druckman, J. N., Drury, J., Dube, O., Ellemers, N., Finkel, E. J., Fowler, J. H., Gelfand, M., Han, S., Haslam, S. A., Jetten, J., Kitayama, S., Mobbs, D., Napper, L. E., Packer, D. J., Pennycook, G., Peters, E., Petty, R. E., Rand, D. G., Reicher, S. D., Schnall, S., Shariff, A., Skitka, L. J., Smith, S. S., Sunstein, C. R., Tabri, N., Tucker, J. A., van der Linden, S., van Lange, P., Weeden, K. A., Wohl, M. J. A., Zaki, J., Zion, S. R., & Willer, R. (2020). Using social and behavioural science to support COVID-19 pandemic response. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 1-12. DOI: 10.1038/s41562-020-0884-z.

Verloo, M. (2013). Intersectional and cross-movement politics and policies. *Signs*, 38(4), 893-915. <https://doi.org/10.1086/669572>.

Walby, S. (2015). *Crises*. Bristol: Polity Press.

Walby, S., Armstrong, J., & Strid, S. (2012). Intersectionality. Multiple tensions in social theory. *Sociology*, 46(2), 224-240. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003803851141616>.

Walter, L. A., & McGregor, A. J. (2020). Sex- and gender-specific observations and implications for COVID-19. *The Western Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 21(3), 507-509. doi: 10.5811/westjem.2020.4.47536.

Živković, I., Kerremans, A., & Denis, A. (2022). *RESISTIRÉ - Agenda for Future Research - 1st Cycle*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5846267>.

